

OUTLOOK

Visions and research directions for the Wireless World

Millennial Users in a 5G Context

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White Paper
Millennial Users in a 5G Context

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Executive Summary

The Millennial generation born between 1982 and 2004 constitute the biggest generation ever worldwide. It is the first generation with a tight digital life and at the same time also an understanding of what was before. It is expected that the Millennial generation can have specific requirements for future digital networks and services according to their skills, knowledge and expectation levels.

This paper presents a picture of the Millennial generation and discussions of their requirements to the upcoming 5G networks. The paper looks at the Millennial generation at a general level (through literature) and presents empirical work with focus groups run to discuss specific 5G network issues.

The literature study presents the Millennial generation as a diverse group of individuals who are used to working, playing and just being online all the time. Millennials are at the leading edge of the social phenomenon of being on social media. They are leading in the use of Internet, mobile technology, social media, etc. and use the technology to construct personalised networks of friends, colleagues and affinity groups. 81% of Millennials are on Facebook. The Millennials are careful in terms of who can be trusted online, just 19% of Millennials say that most people can be trusted (much higher numbers for other generations). However, the Millennials have also been hit hard by economic recession and generally poor economy conditions, but in spite of this they are optimistic, ambitious and have a strong desire to make it to the top of their professions.

Two focus groups were held in order to elucidate the expectations to and requirements of 5G. As part of the focus groups, small movies were shown presenting the visions and use cases of 5G to support the attempt to conceptualize what 5G would mean to them, the recurring ideas centred on the personal utility they would derive from 5G, the cost of accessing the service and the security implications of the network. In addition, they discussed scenarios of possible use cases, security and adoption challenges surrounding the use cases. Hence, one would say that these Millennials had an idea about the 5G concept but were yet to be convinced on what and how they could benefit from it. They did not see a need for 5G in the visions presented but were rather satisfied with the level of connectivity lying in 4G.

The paper concludes that Millennials have expectations that 5G will happen as a natural development and progress. They do not see themselves to have an interest or pay for all implementations of all 5G use cases but only for the ones with direct relevance for them. Also, privacy and security is a key factor that they expect to be managed in some way. Early characteristics of the generation following the Millennials, the Centennials are included.

1. Introduction

Millennials represent the first generation being brought up with Internet and a diversity of devices during their entire lives. Being born around the years of 1982-2004¹, Millennials are currently adults pursuing education, establishing themselves and working as a central part of the workforce. For years, this particular generation has been researched with the purpose to understand the impact that the Internet and focus on technology have had on them as well as how this will influence future advances in technologies. Porras et al. (2014) provide one insight into this by taking a look at the requirements for future technology developments and general societal changes.

Millennials have formed their lives around many digital services such as social media as well as work related platforms and have all of their lives been part of a continuous change and improvements in terms of digital devices, Internet access and speed. However, will that do anything to their demands and expectations for future Internet and services?

Internationally, there has been a focus on defining, understanding and now exploring and developing 5G network capabilities and functionalities and other parameters (see for example IEEE, 2016). One of the central parts within this work is a specific focus on user needs defined by various application areas (see for example European Parliament, 2016) to define specific features of the 5G networks. The user needs and expectations thereby become a central factor in the development and exploration of 5G.

The 5G networks have within the last years been defined in various ways. Figure 1 shows one of the visions as expressed by Huawei (2013).

Figure 1: Overview of Huawei 5G vision with capabilities and use cases (Huawei, 2013)

This paper focuses on understanding requirements from the Millennial generation that must be met in a 5G implementation. The Millennial generation is the first generation to be always on 24/7.

¹ There is no agreed definition of *Millennials*, but it is usually applied to the group who reached adulthood around the turn of the 21st century. William Strauss and Neil Howe are often credited with coining the term in *Generations: The History of America's Future, 1584 to 2069*, Strauss and Howe where they defined Millennials as being born between 1982 and 2004.

Furthermore, Millennials represent the largest group of people in the US (PewResearch, 2014) and a major influential group anywhere, which is why there is a special focus on this generation to understand requirements for future 5G developments.

This paper builds on the WWRF Outlook on “Users 2020 A WWRF Vision” published in 2014 (Porrás et al, 2014) that provides a background to understanding different generations and their technological needs for future technologies. However, in this paper focus is solely on the Millennials since the group is seen to be the generation that can/will set the requirements for 5G. The paper will present user requirements for 5G developments and implementations based on understanding the Millennial behaviour and general characteristics.

The paper is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the historical background, which has formed most Millennials. Section 3 gives the general characteristics of the Millennial generation. Section 4 is an empirical analysis built on focus group interviews of Millennials and discussing needs and expectations to 5G. Based on this information, along with the general understanding of the Millennials, the paper suggests user requirements, which should be used as a basis for defining and deploring 5G networks. Section 5 presents an overview of studies about Millennials outside the US and Scandinavia. Section 6 presents a summary of requirements found from Millennials associating with 5G. Section 7 presents shortly early characteristics of the generation to follow the Millennials. This also serves to validate the characteristics and requirements found for the Millennials – to see how sustainable they are. Finally, section 8 shows the conclusions. The paper builds on a collaboration between members of World Wireless Research Forum.

2. Circumstances Forming the Millennial Generation

Millennials are, as indicated above, defined as individuals born between 1982 and 2004. This place the millennial generation to be the largest ever and out of this alone there are interests of understanding the characteristics of the generation. Burnstein (2013) estimates that there are 1.7 billion Millennials worldwide – which is almost a third of the people on Earth.

Both international and local societal trends and events have always impacted the generations growing up. However, the international aspects of both crises/wars and trends in cultural norms are more present to the Millennials than to generations before. The Millennial generation has experienced the September 11, 2001 attacks in New York, and the global uncertainties and perspectives of terror. Furthermore, there has in this period been global engagements in several local wars (Burnstein, 2013) – War in the Gulf through the 1980's; Gulf war in Iraq and Kuwait in 1991, War from 2001 in Afghanistan; the start of War of Terror (as a response to the 9/11 attacks in the USA); unfinished war in Iraq 2003-2011; Civil war in Libya from 2011 and war in Syria from 2011. The financial crisis hit around the world in the years 2008-2012. This has globally had an impact on families, jobs, collapsing of companies and national economies and lack of possibilities for many.

Burnstein (2013) mentions that the Millennials as individuals experience the global events in a way that no other generations have. This relates to the big events above and to school shootings announced beforehand on social media, to boys becoming worldwide pop stars through YouTube in a relatively short time, to being able to engage in political debates and matter (again through social media). Furthermore, the Millennials are more than ever starting own not-for-profit organisations in their eagerness to make a difference and matter (Burnstein, 2013).

Burnstein (2013) concludes that all these aspects have taught the Millennials to live and manage uncertainty and to deal with it. Generally, the Millennials have been more positive during the

financial crisis than any other generation. He also concludes that the Millennials perceive the world to be fast changing and that the “fast forward” mode is something which characterises the Millennials.

3. What Do We Know about Millennials?

In Porras et al. (2014) various generations are discussed in terms of characteristics and requirements for future technologies. The paper identifies four areas where it can be foreseen that changes will take place in the immediate future – these relating to technological, societal, environmental and individual levels:

- Technological and scientific level (smarter machines, nanotechnology, 3D printing)
- Societal level (urbanization, globalization, concept of the workforce)
- Energy and environment (climate change as a megatrend, energy as a global need)
- Individual/personal level (personal lives will likely change being more connected yet being more alone).

More details can be found in Porras et al. (2014).

Focusing on getting a better understanding of the key characteristics of the Millennial generation, the above levels will be used to categorise Millennials. The categorisation is built on a literature study. Porras et al. (2014) mention that (Oblinger, 2003) found out that Millennials have a focus on group activity, that they have a fascination with technology and like to do experimental activities, and that they have a general mind-set of an information age, as defined by Frand (2000). The information age mind-set consists of these ten features (Frand, 2000):

- Computers aren't technology
- The Internet is better than TV
- Reality is no longer real
- Doing is more important than knowing
- Learning more closely resembles Nintendo than logic
- Multitasking is a way of life
- Typing is preferred to handwriting
- Staying connected is essential
- Zero tolerance for delays
- Consumer and creator are blurring.

The PewResearch Center did in 2014 make a large survey on characteristics of the Millennials and concluded that the Millennials differ significantly from preceding generations. In 2014, the Millennials were between 13-35 years old. Generally, Millennials are more politically independent, less religiously affiliated, are less married, are much more using technology and social media (sharing selfies twice as much as the preceding generation), they are less trusting than other generations, and a large percentage say that they do not earn enough money now but will in the future.

More details of these characteristics can be found below (from PewResearch, 2014):

- Half of the American Millennials describe themselves as politically independent
- A third of the Millennials are not affiliated with any religion
- Just 26% of the Millennials are married – most would like to marry but say they lack economic foundation to do so
- Millennials are the leading edge of the social phenomenon of being on social media. They are leading in the use of Internet, mobile technology, social media, etc. and use the technology to construct personalised networks of friends, colleagues and affinity groups. 81% of Millennials are on Facebook
- 55% of the Millennials have posted a “selfie” on a social media site
- Millennials are careful in terms of who can be trusted online, just 19% of Millennials say that most people can be trusted (much higher numbers for other generations)
- Millennials are as likely as others to have a favourable view of business, and they are more likely than older generations to say they support activist governments
- Millennials are the first to have a higher level of student loan debts, poverty and unemployment, and lower levels of wealth and personal income than the two preceding generations at the same time in their life cycle (this is mainly a result of the economic recession in 2007-2009). Two thirds of recent bachelor degree students have outstanding loans with an average debt of about 27,000\$ (which is twice the size that the preceding generation had)
- Millennials are generally optimists about the economy. More than 80% say that they have enough money to lead the lives they want. On the other side half of the say that they do not believe that there will be money in the Social Security systems by the time they will have to retrieve
- Millennials are a diverse group with many differing views. White and non-white Millennials have different views on the role of government and political parties
- Generally, the Millennials are more in favour of supporting gay rights, but less patriotic, religious and environmentalist than the preceding generations

Nielsen (2014) did another analysis in which he looked into myths and statements generally said about Millennials. Nielsen (2014) generally characterises the Millennials as: social; connected to social circles via online and mobile; living in dense, diverse urban villages where social interaction is just outside their doors; valuing authenticity and creativity; buying local goods; caring about families, friends; finding social networks even more valuable due to economic challenges. Details about these general elements are summarised in the following (from Nielsen, 2014):

- Millennials care about self-expression but are not self-absorbed. More than a third of the Millennials have a tattoo
- They respond more to celebrity endorsements and to advertising that features celebrities, they are particularly receptive to endorsements by music artists they like. Around 25% of Millennials will try a brand or product if they sponsor an event for a music artist they like.
- They think it is important to take care of older parents and making a social impact. 63% of Millennials feel that they have responsibility for their elderly parents
- The unemployment rate for Millennials is high (13% in 2014 for Millennials between 20-24 years old).

- Being hit hard by economic recession and generally poor economy conditions, they are optimistic, ambitious and have a strong desire to make it to the top of their professions
- In spite of the low income, the Millennials make large donations to non-profit organisations, and they are inclined to do volunteer work much more than preceding generations. Over 60% are willing to pay more for a product if it is good for the environment. And they are much more inclined to spend more for products or services from companies that have implemented programs to give back to the society
- Millennials are conscious about their health – they are interested in help to make healthier choices
- They appreciate a personal touch in dealing with their health – like a check-in call from their health provider with reminders for appointments and health advice
- Younger Millennials (up to 40%) are more open to spend money on alternative medicine and treatments
- Millennials are inclined to stay living in the urban areas in mixed-use communities where they live close to shopping areas, restaurants and offices
- Two thirds of Millennials rent their house/apartment instead of buying. They are much more likely to live with roommates or family (at home) than alone
- 36% rely on financial support from their parents
- Because they live in the urban areas, Millennials are less inclined to buy own cars, they opt for being green, and with a high focus on environmental causes. They are likely to walk to work – and use public transportation
- They are the most educated generation where more than 23% hold a Bachelor degree or higher
- They are more inclined to engage in online trading and to have contact with financial advisors
- Generally, Millennials want the latest and greatest products but must balance the buy with their financial situation. They are likely to focus on discounts and good deals more than any other generations
- Millennials are more likely to visit restaurants with easy Wi-Fi, and chains with app usage (for example where you can buy by using the app or get a discount or reward)
- Millennials have a focus on authenticity when shopping, handmade, vintage, crafts made items are in focus
- Millennials do not shop more online than other generations. Only 6% were shopping online – they still visit the malls and physical shops
- Technology is inherent in the Millennial generation. They were the first to come of age with cable TV, Internet and cell phones. Millennials have a positive view (more than other generations) of how technology affects their lives. More than 74% think that new technology makes their life easier, and 54% think that new technology helps them be closer to their friends and family
- Millennials spend less time watching TV than other generations. 50% of Millennial households do not own a TV but watch content on smartphones and laptops. They watch TV and video content on YouTube. And if they watch TV they prefer participation programs such as “MasterChef”, “America’s got Talent” etc.

- Millennials cannot be stereotyped. They have many different interests and priorities, and a natural interest in customization and individuality
- Millennials care about social issues – they like crowd-sourcing

These results are supported in a survey by Goldman Sachs (2016) that adds an inclination for ‘Access not ownership’ and cites Jeremy Rifkin for ‘25 years from now, car sharing will be the norm, and car ownership an anomaly’.

Burnstein (2013, p.76) references Boyd² for her work on privacy. The way privacy is perceived is changing. From being “privacy by default, public by effort” she says that it is now “public by default, private by effort”. There is a conflict in the way the Millennials live and the concerns about privacy. Millennials are generally aware of the privacy challenges; however, they are not willing to give up the “one clicks”, and benefits of being online all the time, and therefore generally they do not take action (Burnstein, 2013, p. 77).

4. Millennial User Requirements – Focus Groups

From the above it is clear that the Millennials will have decisive influence on how and to what extent future 5G services are accepted and how successful services will be shaped. In order to identify user requirements for 5G, two focus group interviews were set up. The focus group was considered to be a beneficial way of involving Millennials in an analysis, since the 5G as a theme – as all future services - is expected to be a difficult subject to discuss, without prior knowledge or interest. In a focus group setting, all participants can chip in when they want and they can build on others’ knowledge and thoughts. On the other hand, the focus group can also influence on participants’ thinking about a topic bringing an appearance of consensus where there perhaps is none (Berg, 2009).

4.1 Set-Up of the Focus Group

Two focus group interviews took place at Aalborg University Copenhagen. Ads were placed around campus to attract all interested persons in ages between 18 and 37 years. This could potentially be students, technical staff, professors, janitors and persons working in the canteen and similar places, and since the ad was in English and the campus has 50% foreign (non-Danish) students, there could be representatives from all types of countries and cultures. Two focus groups were held since at different times to attract as many persons as possible. Both focus groups were set up and conducted as described below.

The focus groups consisted of a total of 16 students (7+9 people) who signed up for a one-hour talk about 5G. Coffee/tea and cake was provided. In Table 1, an overview can be found of a few characteristics of the participants. The focus group interviews were tape recorded, followed by a short survey with information on the individual (such as age etc.). The focus groups were organised in the following way:

- First an introduction was given to the purpose of the focus group. A small YouTube video (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vwywdylnbEo>) was shown describing the developments

² Danah Boyd is a researcher at Microsoft Research and the founder of the book *Data & Society* (www.danah.org). She has done substantial research on young people and their use of social media and everyday practice with a particular focus on privacy.

from 2G to 4G as a basis for discussions about knowledge and own experiences with changing connectivity.

- Then discussions were held about participants' views and expectations of 5G. This was followed by a short YouTube video (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ikR0_ptc4P4) with a company's view on 5G. Discussions were then held about this and new ideas.
- The focus group ended with a survey and coffee/cake session.

PARTICIPANT	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
GENDER	M	M	M	M	M	F	M	F	F	F	M	M	M	M	M	M
AGE	23	26	20	27	26	25	24	27	24	23	26	25	24	24	32	25

Table 1 Overview of the participants in the focus group interviews. M is Male, F is Female

Common for all participants is that they are international students at the Aalborg University Copenhagen, and they consider themselves IT savvy. All of them use 4G on their smart phones. All participants use common IT services such as: social networking, e-mails, VoIP and streaming.

4.2 Results of the Focus Group

The interview was transcribed. Thematic analysis was used later to analyse the data. A summary of the results is presented below. Details and the raw data can be obtained by contacting the authors.

The participants were asked a number of questions relating to three themes:

- Views and experience of the respondents with 4G technology and services
- Impression of 5G without any details or information
- Impression of 5G after watching a video about 5G

Participants' Impression of 4G

The participants did express their views on how they view 4G as a technology and the services 4G provided. All the participants were 4G subscribers. The participants became 4G subscribers by purchasing their mobile phone as an inherent part of the subscription. They did not decide on the upgrade from 3G to 4G even though they co-exist naturally in Denmark, where they currently live. The participants were interested in 4G due to the following reasons (extracted from the themes): The utility provided by the technical and service possibilities of 4G, the marketing strategy of the mobile network operator, network accessibility and the access cost.

- Utility
 - i. Technical possibilities of 4G: Connectivity, reliability and the data rates provided by 4G were important factors to the respondent using 4G. The users were satisfied with the fact that they could:
 - a. connect to the Internet anywhere and at any time. They could also use their mobile phones as access points in situations where Wi-Fi connectivity was insufficient.
 - b. have access to the same quality of service for the services they access anywhere and at any time.
 - c. access 4G services with lower latency and higher data rates.

- ii. Service possibilities enabled by 4G: Based on the technical possibilities of 4G, the respondents were able to access enhanced service delivery. These enhanced services included streaming services, entertainment possibilities and other life enhancing functionalities. Such life enhancing functionalities include location based services, etc.
- Network Operator Strategy
 - i. The service delivery strategy by the network operator: The respondents did not adopt 4G because they had a choice. They did so because:
 - a. They bought new Subscriber Identification Modules (SIMs) from providers that provided 4G.
 - b. Their mobile network operator upgraded to 4G.
Hence, they were beneficiaries of a supply push strategy of their mobile network operator.
 - ii. Service packaging of 4G: Some of the respondents adopted 4G because the network operators provide 4G as a commodity.
- Cost
 - i. Affordable access devices: The respondents responded to the supply push because they could afford the hardware and software needed for the 4G services they needed.
- Network Accessibility
 - i. The level of national coverage of 4G provided by the operator: TDC, one of the 4G Network operators, has nationwide coverage in Denmark. This was the reason why some respondents adopted their 4G service.

Further comments: Half of the respondents are challenged by a higher battery consumption using 4G. Also, half of the respondents still experience inconsistent connectivity with 3G and 4G especially when travelling.

Participants' Impression of 5G without Getting Information

The participants were discussing the following expectations and views before a video on 5G was shown to them. These discussions and views were grouped into themes and discussed.

- Conservative view of 5G: 5G will be a mobile evolution and not a revolution – meaning it will likely be an upgrade of 4G and not a radical innovation. The participants think that the Internet of Things, virtual reality and self-broadcasting already exists so these services will be implemented to a greater extent with 5G.
- New Business cases: The respondents expect business models for 5G to evolve. This will be based on the type of service delivered and the existing market possibilities.
- Technical possibilities beyond 4G: There are expectations that 5G will provide higher data rates and bandwidth. 5G will provide greater capacity for the Internet of Things. There are also expectations that 5G will enable more real-time data delivery.
- Endless application possibilities: As 5G is expected to be an evolution of 4G, the respondents' thought of endless application possibilities for 5G. Such applications include:
 - i. More interaction via virtual broadcasting.
 - ii. Efficient navigation possibilities.
 - iii. Ubiquitous connectivity via Internet of Things.
 - iv. Big data mining possibilities.

- v. Efficient virtual reality in gaming possibilities.
 - vi. Lucid video transmission of 4K and 8K videos.
 - vii. Unimaginable applications that will be developed
 - viii. New hardware application for Internet of things. The respondents believe that the current hardware application for Internet of Things is not suitable for 5G as they are low-powered devices.
- Impact on current state of life: 5G will not be a surprise to people that are technologically savvy and vice versa. Hence for those who are not technologically savvy, some applications may disrupt their way of life, as it will be new.
 - Why 5G?: The respondents think that 4G's potential has not been harnessed. Most of what they mentioned, they believe 4G can facilitate it. Hence, they wondered, "why 5G?".

Participants' Impression of 5G after watching the Video

The participants were discussing the following expectations and views after the video on 5G was shown to them:

- General impression of 5G from the video: The general view of the respondents after watching the video was that of uncertainty. The respondents could not conceive what 5G really is and were inundated by different visions shown. The 5G concept was initially viewed as overwhelming. This was because the respondents believed it was impossible to conceive how certain use cases will be adopted in real life by society. An example was the case of smart wearables. The uncertainty extended to:
 - i. The personal adoption of 5G: One of the respondents confessed that "he does not see himself pay for 5G" as he is not sure how some of the services will be useful to him.
 - ii. Business model uncertainty: The respondents were not sure how the business cases will be developed for the services.
 - iii. The autonomous car use cases: The respondents were not sure of how the autonomous cars will operate.
 - iv. Home appliance uncertainty: The respondents were also not certain about the home appliances that will aid services like virtual reality in the home.

Though the respondents had uncertainties, they felt the video presented a technology utopia, a new way of life and mobile broadcast revolution. Some respondents also expressed pessimism towards the achievability of the 5G visions (they have seen the same visions before 3G and 4G and do not think they are there). Also, the respondents expressed some concern that the visions about 5G not will be useful to them.

- 5G as an evolved 4G: The respondents were not so certain if 5G will be a mobile revolution or evolution. But they still maintained that they see an evolution of 4G. This is because:
 - i. The services were not so different from what 4G could facilitate.
 - ii. Internet of Things exists today with 4G
 - iii. 4G also enables new video possibilities.
 - iv. The services were more of evolved 4G services. Hence, they were not so new.
- Conceptual divergence of 5G: The respondents viewed 5G services as very pervasive or person centric. They wondered how dynamic human needs will cater for by the network operators.

They were unsure if people will really need these services, as people and their needs are segmented from the personal, cultural and geographic dimensions. They also felt that the applications needed for 5G will be very divergent and one cannot conceive what new applications would emerge.

- New technical possibilities: The respondents agreed that real time data delivery and high throughput is expected from 5G.
- Specific use cases: The respondents identified some specific use cases such as:
 - i. Big data possibilities: The use of big data from transportation to control of traffic. They further explained that there would be lots of huge data possibilities from different fields. This would aid in various analytics initiatives.
 - ii. Transportation: One of the respondents mentioned, public transportation as a potential use case. Another in the same vein mentioned the use of self-driving cars for very short distances and only for emergency situations.
 - iii. Ubiquitous use cases: Smart city possibilities and the pervasive usage of 5G in cities were mentioned as possibilities. It was difficult for them to be specific.
- Personal doubts on 5G: Some of the respondents wondered how service delivery via ubiquitous connectivity will be achieved in the face of cultural divergence and divergent personal needs.
- Satisfaction with connectivity as it is now: Some of the respondents said that they were actually rather satisfied with the connectivity as it is now. They were rather satisfied using Wi-Fi and use of VoIP and do not see the need for Voice over LTE, as an example.
- Hardware immaturity: Some respondents mentioned that the devices are immature for 5G. They feel the devices have to evolve as the technology evolves. If this does not occur, then they envisage a device to network incompatibility.
- Hardware unreliability: A respondent felt that sensors will be unreliable for 5G. This is because sensors are low powered; its life span may be short for 5G connectivity. This would be the case in smart wearables. They suggest sensors with longer battery life.
- Hardware security: The respondents were not certain how secured the sensors will be in smart wearables.
- Personal safety issues: The respondents felt 5G presented personal safety issues. The safety concerns were based on the unforeseen circumstances and personal data safety issues. Unforeseen circumstances include traffic accident caused by signal malfunction, cyber-attacks in automated cars and cyber security in self-driving cars. Personal safety issues involved data and user confidentiality in self-driving cars. Such security bridges could affect the functioning of the self-driving cars.
- Security threats: The respondents felt that the security in the usage of 5G services will be an issue. These security issues include:
 - i. Unforeseen threats or latent threats: These are security threats we cannot envisage now.
 - ii. The lack of trust in current security initiatives by the respondents.
 - iii. User apathy towards personal data security: Here the respondents explained that users generally value the benefit of connectivity above security. Users are only alarmed when there is a leakage in personal data.

- iv. The inefficiency of current data solutions: The respondents were uncertain about how the network operators use their personal information, and how it affects their security. They mentioned that they probably would be more aware of security if they had experienced hacker attacks. They think the EU is taking steps to solve security issues,
 - v. but they are not aware of global initiatives. Hence if they leave the EU, how secured is their data? They also wished there were simultaneous or ready solutions to security and privacy issues.
 - vi. The lack of trust for current security solutions: One of the concerns raised was, whether security stakeholders are keen on solving current security problems.
- Privacy Control: The respondents were unanimous in agreeing that it is the user that should control personal data. The users should be able to decide, whether to disclose or allow others to use or store their data. They also mentioned that the users should have the power to retrieve their data.
 - Solution for security: The respondents felt the network operator should be the entity that defines the privacy and security guidelines in a 5G environment. They feel that security on the connectivity infrastructure is more critical than security on the application. Hence they feel that the application providers do not have the incentives to set up security guidelines in a 5G environment. But it is easy to hold the network operators accountable, if there is a bridge, since everything centres on connectivity. The respondents said that they would consider paying for security as a service.
 - Battery consumption: The respondents expressed high concern about battery consumption for 5G. They would prefer lower battery consumption to data rates.

Summary of Findings

The adoption of 4G technology and services by the respondents enabled them to access mobile telecom services in new ways. So far the mobile telecom services they have access to are similar to what they could access with 3G networks. However, with 4G, they experience constant connectivity and better quality of service at an affordable cost. One would say that their utility of mobile telecom services has been built gradually over the years with evolutions in mobile telephony. One would say that this hampered their view on 5G - which is of course yet to be defined. However, in their attempt to conceptualize what 5G will mean to them, the recurring ideas centred on the personal utility they would derive from 5G, the cost of accessing the service and the security implications of the network. This is of course influenced by how they see the 4G ecosystem.

In addition to the above they have raised interesting scenarios of possible use cases, the security and adoption challenges surrounding the use cases. Hence, one would say that this group of Millennials have an idea about the 5G concept but are yet to be convinced on what is in it for them. They do not see a need for 5G in the visions presented but are rather satisfied with the level of connectivity lying in 4G.

5. Millennials of the World

Many of the references used so far as well as the empirical workshop are based on Scandinavian and US studies. As already stated in this paper, it is not possible to generalise from these studies to the Millennial generation across the World. There are of course many other trends as well as variations dependent on culture, economy of the country, infrastructure and many other parameters.

	ATTITUDES TOWARDS LIFE	CONNECTION AND COMMUNICATION	FINANCES
CHINA	Independent thinkers where more than half are independent on what others think. Family is important for decision making and there is a challenge in balancing traditional Chinese values with the modern lifestyle	Think laptops are equally important to smartphones. Use of social media is strong	70 % of Chinese Millennials use Internet for financial matters. 94% of Millennials shop frequently shop online
RUSSIA	62% of Millennials have a goal to become entrepreneurs.	Connection is important. 70% of Millennials use computers for emailing, searching information and sending/sharing pictures. Instant messaging and chatrooms are used on phones	70% of Millennials have savings. Only 29% have an insurance. 85% shop online
INDIA	4 out of 5 Millennials are ambitious and dream big. Strong work ethics. Parents are influencing on financial matters	Use computers and mobiles for work and study. One in two access social networking sites on a weekly basis	85% of Millennials save around 20% of their monthly income. Study and tuition fee loans account for 18% each. 73% shop online but only 44% of these on a frequent, weekly basis
SOUTH AFRICA	Enjoy simple, precious things in life and are ambitious	89% have a computer and 80% a smart phone, 50% have TV. Computers are used for emailing, surfing the Internet and banking	68% save a part of their monthly income. They save to do shopping
UNITED ARAB EMIRATES	95% are ambitious and with big dreams. 94% see themselves as leaders and with a life of achievements	Staying connected is important. 75% use computers and 38% use mobile phones. 95% use Facebook once a week. 59% own a smartphone and it is the most important gadget	62% do savings. Shopping is the main purpose of saving. 67% believe that electronic payment will displace cash in the future.

Table 2 Summary of country studies of Millennials' attitudes towards life, connection and communication means and finances (from Visa, 2011)

A study from Visa (2011) has compared surveys amongst Millennials in 11 countries (a total of 5500 respondents from Singapore, Philippines, Indonesia, China, Hong Kong, Taiwan, Korea, Russia, India, South Africa, United Arab Emirates). The survey gives information about the Millennials' attitudes toward life and family values, how they connect and communicate, and their attitudes to finance, expenditures, shopping and banking. In the table 2, five of the 11 countries are summarized in terms of attitudes towards life, connection and communication preferences, and financial elements. Further country studies and details can be found in the Visa (2011) document.

Generally, the Millennials can be characterised in similar words, even though there are differences in how important some features are to the Millennials in different locations. The survey is, however, from 2011, and with globalization progressing there may be some changes in these figures and characteristics today.

Other sources have found other characteristics and facts about the Millennials:

- “with more than 200 million millennials between 15 and 24 in Africa, the majority of future technology pioneers would come from Africa’s millennial generation, given that they are the largest population of young people in the world” (Counted and Arawole, 2016)
- generally African Millennials are connected to the Internet however, they are yet to realise the potential of the Internet technology due to lack of significant usage access to online opportunities (Counted and Arawole, 2016)
- Mexican Millennials are satisfied with their lives (35% say they are satisfied) in contrast to the Japanese Millennials where only 10% say they are satisfied with life (Iris Millennials, 2015)
- In France, only 17% of the Millennials are optimistic about the future (Iris Millennials, 2015)
- 66% of German Millennials are satisfied with the direction of their country, in UK this number is 53% and in Italy it is 11%, while in Greece just 6% (Pewresearch Center, 2014)
- 88% of Millennials (from a Deloitte, 2016 study³) wish they would have a greater opportunity to work remotely and to decide on starting and finishing times of the work. Furthermore, 77% of Millennials (ibid) would like to have a greater mobile connectivity.

Many of the variations seen in the different countries in terms of Millennial preferences are linked very much to the economic and social status and situation of the country.

6. Summary of Millennials and 5G User Requirements

Based on the literature review about Millennial users and the focus group, a number of thoughts and expectations is identified that can lead to requirements for 5G. This comes into 4 different areas:

- **Internet and 5G:** Millennials generally expect continued, fast developments in technologies/networks. They do not see 5G as anything special – it is only special for the IT savvy people. It is expected that 5G as a network will exist as a combination of different types of networks. 5G is seen as the real implementation of IoT. Millennials generally do not have a manifest need for higher data rates.
- **Price:** There is an expectation that 5G can be offered to the customers through different variations of network combinations and that this can form the possibility for service

³ The Deloitte (2016) study is based on 4300 interviews in 16 Emerging Markets countries and in 12 developed markets countries. These numbers go across the variations in markets.

providers to offer different price combinations to the customer. The 5G networks and services must generally not command higher prices than 4G. The Millennials will only pay extra for 5G if it is directly useful for them.

- **Privacy/trust:** Millennials do generally not trust app developers. The service developers must earn the Millennials' trust in some ways – the trust is not there as default. Privacy is important for the Millennials. In 5G services, privacy must be easy to handle and be present by default. Millennials expect to be in control of their data in the future. Many of the IoT services relating to the 5G vision hinge on privacy and this must be solved (for example the self-driving cars and tracking of foot-prints generally). Security is a factor that is expected to be addressed and dealt with.
- **Battery:** The Millennials would prefer higher battery life time to data rates.

The above results are based on a combination of literature review and data collected through focus group interviews. This focus group interview was run with a small number of participants. Also, the participants were from a university and only two focus group interviews were conducted.

7. After the Millennials

In order to understand how sustainable, the above-mentioned requirements are, the characteristics of the generation following the Millennials are discussed below. As seen above, the behavioural patterns and requirements of the Millennials are emerging as quite well-developed, but now the next cohort, Generation Z/ the Centennials born after 1995 – or after 2000, enters the stage⁴. They have, however, hardly yet entered as a decisive socio-economic group with own characteristics. Characterisations by consultancies and media analysts started out declaring that we have now a new group emerging, very different from Millennials, but in reality, vaguely differentiated as 'Millennials+', i.e. they are more always on; better multitaskers; more global. There are, however, signs that the Centennials can be identified by specific characteristics. As for the Millennials, the search for specific characteristics of the Centennials is driven by the marketing industry as they will constitute 40% of the consumers in 2020 (OrderDynamics 2016).

Summarizing some characteristics from different analyses:

- Facebook use is toned down in favour of visual communication as Snapchat and Instagram (OrderDynamics 2016 and Wall Street Journal 2017)
- They are better multitaskers, shift quickly between work and play; are more entrepreneurial and more globally oriented (Beall 2016)
- They have even more access to smartphones and use less time meeting friends physically, more virtually facilitated by, e.g. House party, Families, Tribe (Wall Street Journal 2017). One consequence of this is decreasing juvenile criminality documented in a Danish survey (Balvig 2017). There is simply less time to engage in criminal activities.

This seems in line with the Millennials' requirements to 5G, with the qualification that the increasing use of visual communication may result in real demand for the higher bandwidth delivered by 5G.

⁴ As for Millennials, there is no generally agreed definition – often those born between 1995 and 2015 – or in this case even of the name Generation Z; Centennials or iGen (see e.g., The Center for Generational Kinetics, 2016)

8. Conclusions

The focus of the paper is on understanding, which expectations Millennials, with a view to the following cohort: The Centennials, as a generation have for the upcoming 5G networks. The Millennials being the largest generation present at the time and the first generation who has been growing up as digitals with Internet, cloud services, social media, smart phones and tablets. The work on 5G networks is underway, and this work is seen as an input to the service providers in respect to understanding their customers – the Millennials.

The paper concludes that the Millennials generally do not see 5G as anything special but just as another expected development of the Internet. There are expectations that the development will continue the 4G trend and happen as a natural continuation. The Millennials expect that the visions of IoT will come true with 5G, however, they do not want to pay for these services if the services do not seem of relevance to them. They expect 5G to be cheap; that it is available anytime anywhere – facilitating, e.g. the sharing economy; and that it comes with different subscription possibilities relating to the network efficiency. Also, the Millennials are aware of trust, privacy and security issues relating to the vision of 5G and the full implementation of IoT. They expect these areas to be addressed in 5G and to the extent they can also self-manage. Finally, the Millennials generally prefer battery life to higher data rates.

The paper is based on a literature study as well as focus group interviews with a limited number of students (on the borderline between Millennials and Centennials). The paper should therefore be seen as a basis for further work.

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